

LISA BULLETIN

NEWS FOR THE LISA INNOVATIVE TRAINING NETWORK

FEBRUARY 2021, No 1

Here is our first LISA newsletter - intended as a means of keeping you all up to date with news of the network progress, highlights, activities and opportunities. 2020 was a challenging year to get started with a new training network which relies heavily on international collaboration and travel. Even the recruitment of the 15 Early stage researchers has to respect the 'mobility rule' for Marie Curie ITNs, with each researcher relocating abroad for their new role. Despite this, the LISA network has been established and already feels like a productive and friendly community. I am sure everyone is excited to meet in person in 2021 as soon as it becomes possible. Wishing you all a healthy and successful 2021! - Bruce Marsh.

Who are we?

ESRs from 1 to 15. Made by Magdalena Kaja (ESR 05) for [Instagram @lisa_itn](#).

The Laser Ionisation and Spectroscopy of Actinides Innovative Training Network (LISA ITN) is a consortium formed by 15 Early Stage Researchers (ESR) from all over the world, working along side with our 12 beneficiaries and 13 partners. The consortium is divided into 8 Work Packages (WP), from which four are formed by the ESRs only (WP2-WP5). Right now, 14 out of 15 ESRs already started their work and are currently or in the process to be enrolled in a PhD program. Over the next bulletins, we will introduce each ESR and their research, as well as give you an overview of the latest events and information of upcoming events of relevance. In this first edition we introduce our Network Coordinator, [Bruce Marsh](#) and Training Officer, [Thomas Cocolios](#).

Beneficiaries:

Partners:

Interview: LISA Coordination

Bruce Marsh

LISA Network
Coordinator

What motivated you to join the LISA project?

In recent years our community of laser spectroscopists and radioactive ion beam scientists nurtured a friendly and productive network, enabled by several European funded initiatives (such as ENSAR, ENSAR 2 and the LA3NET training network).

As the funding period for ENSAR 2 came to an end we were keen to find a means of continuing our collaboration, but also expanding it to encourage new young researchers to the field, and also to better link our technical needs to the industrial sector. A Marie Curie ITN dedicated to tackling some of the biggest challenges in our field - the study and exploitation of the Actinide elements - seemed like the ideal way to go.

What are the unique characteristics of the project?

I would say that the industrial involvement is very new for us and results in a great opportunity for the researchers to experience both the academic and commercial world. For the field of laser spectroscopy though, it holds a lot of potential: We want to develop commercial-grade laser systems so that the nuclear and atomic physicist can simply use these as tools, rather than having to also become laser physicists and build them themselves! Secondly is the level of inter-connectivity of our 15 ESR projects. All parts (theory, experiment, application, laser) depend upon and contribute to each other. This makes the level of interaction, travel and collaboration of the ESRs logical and even essential, and not at all contrived.

What are your tasks as Coordinator?

My task as the LISA Coordinator evolves throughout the project. It started (together with our TO Thomas) with an intense period of gathering together the consortium, establishing project ideas and concepts and writing the proposal. Next was the recruitment process, led by the CERN HR representative Ingrid Haug. Now we are in the project management phase which requires a general oversight of the project progress to maintain it on the proper trajectory. Thankfully though, I have an excellent project manager (Isabelle Fontaine) working with me at CERN to make sure this goes smoothly.

Are you happy with the first months of the project?

Well, the project success is largely in the hands of our 15 ESRs, so our biggest hurdle to get started was to attract lots of interest and to be able to select excellent candidates. In this respect it couldn't have gone better! All 15 ESRs are now recruited, and have already demonstrated exactly the level of enthusiasm and proficiency that we hoped for! Even the global pandemic hasn't stopped them from getting to know each other, exchanging ideas and beginning their training. COVID 19 has unfortunately delayed some aspects of our plans, inhibited physical meetings and delayed the start date of some ESRs, but we are confident to recover from this and have a very successful project.

Thomas Cocolios
LISA Training Officer

What motivated you to join the LISA project?

Actually, it was Piet Van Duppen who 'volunteered' Bruce and I to create LISA. Since we built it up from scratch, it has been highly motivating from the start! And the two aspects that really drive me are the ESRs – a team of highly motivated young researchers, all looking in the same direction – and the many collaborations that arise from the network.

What are your tasks within this project?

I am the Training Officer, the KU Leuven representative on the LISA Supervisory Board, a member of the Steering Committee (since the MidTerm Review), and Work Package leader for WP3 – Societal impact. Finally, and maybe most importantly, I am the supervisory of ESR1, Jake Johnson, who works on the production of ^{225}Ac for medical applications.

Let's say, LISA is an important part of my activities and a highlight of my work!

The first months of the project.

The recruitment was a big part of the start of the project. It involved posting and distributing the position descriptions, digging into more than 150 applications (and Bruce and I reviewed ALL of them!!), pre-selecting the most suitable, reviewing the videos and interviews until we selected the best of the best. It is impressive that we got all 15 positions filled in the first round – this never happened at CERN!

Once this was completed, it was only a matter of months until the first ESRs started, but that was without counting on the COVID-19 crisis. That definitely threw us off on many levels. We had to adapt the project timeline to account for the delayed start of many ESRs, and the two first trainings had to be majorly rethought to adjust. So a lot of gymnastics but it was all worth it. Seeing the ESRs and Affiliates interact already together this early in the program, we see that the efforts have yielded even more results than we had hoped for and we see a bright project ahead of us.

Additional comments.

This is only the beginning! We have so many plans and ideas for the coming years, for training, for research, for dissemination, for outreach, . . . I am really excited about all of it and I look forward to the meeting where we will all get together and simply sit around a table with a drink, maybe on a beach, and can laugh together.

Past events' highlights!

First Event: LISA Training Kick-off (ONLINE)

by H. GARCÍA

In this initial event, participants were introduced to all the topics of the network and team building activities were used to generate a sense of community.

On the first day, November 20th, 2020, after the welcoming session,

a talk about Business Basic Introduction was given by [Fiona Reid](#), with some group activities. Later that day, the ESRs selected [Lauren Reed ESR 11](#) as a representative to speak in the behalf of all of them. Finally, the day was closed with a Trivia Night put together by [Jake Johnson ESR 01 & Vaila Leask ESR 07](#), where all participants had fun answering obscure questions about zoology and German metal bands. The next day was filled

with talks about Science communication and outreach, given by [Clara Nellist](#) from CERN, professional science communicators [Elizabeth Steib](#) and [Philipp Dettmer](#), and a quick Social Media training by Daniela Antonio.

This event was followed by the LISA Mid-Term Review, which brought together EU officers, consortium members and recruited researchers.

We were all winners! ESRs, affiliates and the LISA Coordination team having online fun.

LISA Mid-Term Review (ONLINE)

by H. GARCÍA

Shortly after the Kick-off event, the LISA Mid-Term Review started with a welcome word from the Network Coordinator, [Bruce Marsh](#), the Research Programme Administrator at the Eu-

ropean Union, [Fabrizio Martone](#), and tour de table for all beneficiaries and partners.

The Work Packages 2, 3 and 5 presented a progress report followed by a short 3-minute presentation of the corresponding ESRs.

On Thursday, November 26th, a

progress report was given related to the Training, Communication, Recruitment of the ESRs and Ethics, as well as a report of the Work Package 4 and a presentation of their corresponding ESRs.

Finally, the week ended with a Supervisory Board meeting and the 2020 Lise Meitner Award Ceremony.

General Training 1 (ON-LINE)

by M. URQUIZA

Starting on Monday, December 7th 2020 until Thursday, December 10th 2020, the first General Training took place completely online due to ongoing Covid-19 pandemic. Regardless of location, this training covered several interesting topics, including a full day about Laser Safety given by IREPA Laser. This event included three talks about Societal impact of the Actinides given by [Ulli Koester](#) from the Institut Laue-Langevin (Fr), [Nathal Severijns](#) from KU Leuven (BE), and [Thorsten Schumm](#) from

TU Wien (AT); and three talks about Applications of lasers given by [Didier Boisselier](#), [Frederic Mermet](#) both from IREPA LASER (Fr) and [Kieran Flanagan](#) from the University of Manchester (GB).

They all were very open to questions and lengthy discussions followed each talk, which made this online format more enjoyable, I am sure.

Mixed with the talks from the experts, there was a brief poster session from each WP, making this the first time the ESRs collaborated together to present their work. At the end of the last day, the Training Officers picked the *best* one out of the

4 posters, the winner this time was **WP5's** poster: Exploring the limits of nuclear existence. Congratulations to all! Finally, following a 3 minute thesis introduction, several LISA affiliates presented themselves to the rest of the ESRs.

As a team building exercise and to compensate for the change of this event's settings, some ESRs and the trainer officer participated in a very personal, very low-cost Secret Santa gift exchange which was revealed after the poster selection. The gifts were all well received with some surprises along the way. Thank you to all who participated!

Women in Science Day 11.02.2021

by M. URQUIZA

The International Day of Women and Girls in Science Assembly brings together stakeholders, including high-level government officials, representatives of international organisations,

foundations, the private sector, and civil society, as well as female scientific experts and girls in science advocates from around the world.

For this year's Women in Science Day, [Magdalena Kaja ESR 05](#) and [Julius Wessolek ESR 09](#) featured some scientist from our Network

on [Instagram @lisa_itn](#) and [Twitter @LISA_ITN](#), respectively, to celebrate the day and to meet some of the talented female scientist working in and with the LISA ITN.

Thank you so much for participating and thank you, Julius and Magdalena, for your work!

Deliverables and milestones: Where are we at?

by I. FONTAINE

Deliverables and milestones are common tools to determine and verify the progress and measure the outcome of a project. As a requirements from the EU, several of them have been set on the “path” of the LISA project.

Since LISA started, deliverables mainly related to the project set up have been submitted and validated by the EU. We consequently completed our first deliverables by launching LISA with its Kick-off meeting (D1.1/ D29) and defining its Supervisory Board (D1.7/ D35), and followed in spring 2020 by completing our ESRs recruitment (D1.2/ D30) and having the [LISA official web-page](#) (D7.1/ D26) online. Despite COVID-19 getting in without notice and surely delaying most of our work, with

the kind support of the CERN design team and EU communication office, we have recently finalized the Promotional aspects (D7.2/D27) linked to the LISA branding and design. You might have seen some templates already but we will further present their unique work in future editions.

With 2021 starting, the work done by the Training Office on assisting ESRs in their ICDP (Individual Career Development Plan) has been completed, (D6.1 / D22); confirming ESRs enrolment in PhD programs (D6.2/ D23) is currently finalized. The data management plan (D1.4/ D32), establishing data management planning and guidance have needed some further thoughts and is also planned to be shortly submitted.

As the LISA Ethic committee was formed and compiled an Ethic Questionnaire to all beneficiaries, an ethic assessment will be shared (D1.3/D31) in the coming month.

Finally, but not the least, on the scientific side, [Jessica Warbinek ESR 10](#) completed an excellent Technical Design Report on **Optimum filament setup for efficient Lr evaporation** (WP5, MS21), topic to be featured in the second quarterly newsletter of this year.

As this first newsletter is now launched, we will also be excited to share in future edition more details on the progress made from the scientific side!

Available positions, events and resources of interest.

Event	Description	More information
Jena Atomic Calculator (JAC code) 	JAC, is a simple and powerful platform for atomic computations: calculation of atomic structures (HFS, isotope shifts, g- & form factors, ...), processes (Auger, photoexcitation & emission, photoionization & recombination, dielectronic recombination, ...), complex atomic cascades and others . JAC has been designed and implemented in Julia in order to be an easy-to-learn & interactive platform for performing various atomic computations and simulations. You are welcome to join this project or to request for additional features to this code.	JAC on Github. News about JAC. Overview to JAC. Brief description. User Guide & Compendium.

Event	Description	More information
<p>Post-Doc (d/f/m) in the area of nuclear physics, sensor technology, MAPS and instrumentation at GSI.</p>	<p>GSI aims to strengthen the engagement in CMOS active pixel sensor technology. These novel highly granular and ultra-thin silicon pixel sensors provide groundbreaking progress for numerous applications in subatomic physics including high-precision charged particle tracking and vertex reconstruction. Together with its international partners of the EU-Cremlin+ initiative, GSI participates in the development endeavor of a next generation of those sensors and the corresponding technologies for integration into complex detector systems. The related research activities cover commissioning and tests of latest sensor prototypes, the mechanical integration of the 50µm thin devices and building a suited high-bandwidth DAQ system.</p>	<p>Application deadline: February 22, 2021. Posting ID: 21.05-771100. For more information here.</p>
<p>Journées des Actinides 2021 and 13th School on the Physics and Chemistry of the Actinides</p>	<p>Following the JdA cancellation due to Covid19 pandemic in 2020, and with the current worldwide sanitary conditions, it is our pleasure to invite you to participate to the 2021 ON-LINE edition of the 13th School on the Physics and Chemistry of the Actinides and 50èmes Journées des Actinides, organized by the "Institut des Sciences Chimiques de Rennes" (France). Abstract submission and (free) registration are open!</p>	<p>From 22-25 March. The deadline for abstracts submission is 12 Feb. and the one for registration is 26 Feb. Please visit conference website.</p>
<p>Special Postdoctoral Researcher (SPDR) for FY2022</p>	<p>The involvement of creative young scientists is critical in pioneering new frontiers of science and technology. RIKEN's Special Postdoctoral Researcher Program is a program to foster the development of researchers who will become internationally active in the future, and provides creative young scientists with the opportunity to be involved in autonomous and independent research on a topic of their own choosing that is in line with RIKEN objectives and research fields.</p>	<p>Application period: February 1 to April 15, 2021. All the Nishina PI welcomes your applications. More information in English and Japanese.</p>

Newsletter's coordination & edition: [Helena Escudero ESR 13](#) and [Mitzi Urquiza ESR 15](#). For any comment or request, contact us [here](#).

LISA – Laser Ionization and Spectroscopy of Actinides. This Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) Innovative Training Networks (ITN) receives funding from the European Union's H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement no. 861198